

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

nextGenIT
Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023

***"Bringing together
Communities and Platforms"***

November 27th-28th

📍 CNR - Rome, Italy

Plant Sciences

Diego Micheletti

Fondazione Edmund Mach

contact: diego.micheletti@fmach.it